

Managing Editor's Column

Dear Readers:

It is a pleasure to present number 2 of volume 1 of J.UCS with again 5 substantial contributions with a good mix, maybe a bit loaded towards theory.

To make sure that J.UCS is not seen as a mainly theory journal I would like to encourage all editors and readers to advocate J.UCS as a timely medium for the dissemination of research results and surveys concerning **ALL** fields of Computer Science.

The reaction to the first two issues has been good. I will compile a detailed breakdown of usage after the half-year mark for information. However, one point is clearly emerging: the current hypertext formats such as HTF or HTML are not well suited for formula-rich material, since even simple formulae like x squared, i.e. x^2 have to be inserted as inline images. This is due to the fact that HTML does not handle anything but text and inline images. Thus, the PostScript version of the documents should be preferred, at least for formula-rich material.

The PostScript version can be used in conjunction with the native Hyper-G viewers Amadeus and Harmony but also with other Webviewers such as Mosaic or NetScape if installed properly with a ghostview viewer. For details see the general description how to do this in the general section of J.UCS.

Finally, it is a pleasure to see that more and more J.UCS servers are becoming publicly available. So to read J.UCS, use the one "nearest" to you (in terms of Internet topology!)...or consider installing a server yourself. All software and instructions are available free for all non-profit organisations by just contacting Klaus Schmaranz at kschmar@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at.

If you have any comments on the journal, please do send me an email to hmaurer@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at.

Thanks for your support of J.UCS!

With best wishes

Hermann Maurer, Managing Editor
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